

Benefit-sharing and the new multilateral mechanism for Digital Sequence Information:

Avoiding past as prologue

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Abstract

The Biodiversity COP established a multilateral mechanism to share benefits from digital sequence information, the details of which will be negotiated over the next two years. As multiple UN fora develop new benefit-sharing systems, now is a critical time for a new, radically simpler concept.

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), adopted by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) at COP15 in December 2022, is a ‘package’ deal with commitments to protect 30 percent of the planet’s surface, and share benefits from the world’s digital biodiversity dataset, known as “digital sequence information” or DSI¹. Parties agreed to create a *multilateral* mechanism for benefit-sharing for DSI, and launched a two-year negotiating process to establish how the mechanism will actually function, including who will be required to share benefits, and under what conditions. In parallel, three other UN fora, the Food and Agriculture Organization², the World Health Organization^{3,4}, and the Convention on the Law of the Seas⁵ have DSI on their agendas. The international community has an opportunity to develop a harmonized DSI framework that is simple, effective, and transformational in its approach to benefit-sharing. In this pivotal moment, we look at Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) in the rearview mirror to learn from prior approaches.

What has ABS taught us so far?

The concept that benefits from the utilization of genetic resources (GR) should be equitably shared is well established, and is one of the primary objectives of several international agreements over the last thirty years. In fact, parties agreed under the GBF to increase benefits shared by 2030. The principle of benefit-sharing has helped to facilitate political compromise⁶, raise awareness of national sovereign and IPLC rights over GR, and encourage companies to engage in responsible sourcing. However, it has

neither resulted in satisfactory benefit-sharing to support biodiversity conservation (or other nationally determined priorities) nor substantially increased access to GR if at all^{7,8}.

We hypothesize that a fundamental disconnect exists between the laudable policy vision of benefit-sharing and its implementation. If latent design flaws are perpetuated, the new DSI mechanism will not deliver on all three objectives of the CBD nor be effective across different UN fora.

It is time for new design principles and solutions

Here we summarize key problems with existing ABS systems based on 30 years of experience and provide recommendations for the new DSI multilateral mechanism.

Problem 1: High transaction costs and low levels of legal certainty

While not required under the CBD or its Nagoya Protocol, many countries have embraced highly granular, individual-transaction-based approaches to access and benefit-sharing. To regulate individual transactions from research to commercialization requires complex systems for evaluating access applications, defining the scope of acceptable uses, identifying benefit-sharing triggers, creating formulas for calculating payments for products derived from multiple GR, developing and approving agreements, tracking and tracing use of accessed materials and the commercialization of derived products, and ensuring enforcement. This complexity imposes unsustainable demands and transaction costs on users, providers, and relevant public officials. It also frequently results in a lack of implementation, legal uncertainty, avoidance and lost opportunities for benefit-sharing. The digital age has amplified this problem but it is inherent to the design itself.

Even under the Plant Treaty's multilateral ABS system, the monetary benefit-sharing formula requires tracking and tracing the use of accessed genetic materials from R&D to commercialization of individual products. Associated high transaction costs, to prove or disprove when payments are due, have driven away commercial users who would otherwise incur benefit-sharing obligations⁹. Moreover, under the nominally standardized PIP framework, lengthy transactions arise in the negotiation of the SMTA2.

Recommendation 1: Radical simplification

Benefit-sharing should be de-coupled from both access and individual products, and contributions should be calculated at an aggregate level. One simple, transparent, and low-transaction-cost approach would be to base payment obligations on national gross domestic product (GDP). Countries whose GDP per capita falls below an established threshold, or similar criteria, could be exempted. The African Group's proposal of a 1% levy on the retail sales of biodiversity-based products represents a step in this direction.

If GDP is too generic to serve as a proxy for DSI utilization, payments could be based on the national aggregate commercial value of pre-agreed sectors (e.g., biotech, pharma, cosmetics) or other statistical metrics (<https://seea.un.org/>). To minimize transaction costs, all participating countries could agree to make initial payments to the global benefit-sharing fund and separately collect from their domestic users based on nationally defined criteria¹⁰. The use of such self-determined formulas would provide flexibility to account for domestic priorities and practices. DSI users in non-parties (the USA) could be allowed to purchase legal certainty by making payments based on a simple formula.

By corollary, it will be important to confirm what DSI is available for use, without restrictions, by users in participating countries. Presumably that should include DSI that is a) currently legally available through open access infrastructures, and b) generated in the future using public funds (with exemptions for, e.g., privacy or IPLC rights). This is already happening; most public funding agencies require publication of research data in open access repositories. Furthermore, contracting parties could create incentives for actors generating DSI with private funds to deposit DSI in open access databases.

Problem 2: Benefit-sharing base is too narrowly defined

Current ABS systems have left many GR and types of use "out of scope" for historical, legal, and political reasons. For example, under the CBD, the majority of GR and the resulting DSI¹¹ in use today is out of material, geographical or temporal scope, largely because most developed countries do not require benefit-sharing. As the complexity of these systems increases (problem 1), users access more materials through unregulated sources.

Current benefit-sharing models largely impose payment obligations on those "utilizing" genetic material, i.e. those users who perform R&D, and miss out on benefit-sharing from a broad range of downstream industries that generate revenue by using technologies developed upstream. Under the Plant Treaty, for example, seed companies are required to make payments, but not international grain merchants or food companies. Under the PIP framework, generic vaccine manufacturers do not pay.

Moreover, individual-transaction-based ABS models exclude those industries and sectors that do not directly use GR, but whose negative externalities contribute to the erosion of biological diversity. Narrow scope also limits non-monetary benefit-sharing to what single users of GR can provide in return for access. This piecemeal approach fails to provide the scale of capacity strengthening that is needed to effectively conserve biodiversity, exploit GR and DSI, and build a circular bioeconomy.

Recommendation 2: Broaden the base for benefit-sharing contributions

Again, radical simplification is key. The legal scope for DSI benefit-sharing obligations must be all-encompassing. A universal scope that covers all types of biological data and "uses of biological diversity" is modern, science-based, and much easier to understand for both providers and users. Material, temporal, and geographical arguments on scope become obsolete if access is fully de-coupled from benefit-sharing.

Problem 3: No guarantee of benefits leads to mistrust and increased restrictions

Dissatisfaction with monetary benefit-sharing under all ABS models to date has perpetuated distrust from many countries who consider themselves to be access-providers. This distrust has led some countries to further restrict GR access¹². Many countries understandably remain reluctant to give up on their bilateral ABS controls and embrace multilateral benefit-sharing when there is no guarantee of monetary benefits being shared directly with them. In such cases, countries are betting on their endemic biodiversity to bring users to the negotiating table.

Even the Plant Treaty's multilateral system of access and benefit-sharing is not designed to fully address this conundrum. Monies are distributed from the Treaty's international benefit-sharing fund through a system of open, competitive bids. Some countries have made repeated bids without being selected, leading to their reluctance to make materials available.

Recommendation 3: Guaranteed benefit-sharing

The new multilateral benefit-sharing mechanism for DSI needs to guarantee minimum benefit-sharing levels for target beneficiaries. Monies could be allocated to dedicated "streams", for example, to support conservation in countries with high levels of biological diversity or biodiversity under threat; to support IPLCs as primary custodians of biodiversity; to develop capacity and technical infrastructure in the global South to make productive use of DSI; to recognize countries proactively giving access to GR used to produce DSI¹³; or to address specific issues (e.g. high seas, sustainable agriculture). There should be a guarantee that all low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) will periodically receive support through one or more of these streams. Negotiators may need to agree upon a formula for minimum payments in this regard.

Problem 4: The growing complexity of life sciences research

The traditional narrative of ABS envisions an exotic plant harnessed to develop a blockbuster drug, under a single benefit-sharing agreement between the providing country and a biotech company. Yet the modern scientific process of biological research and innovation is integrative, systems-based¹⁴. It harnesses a wide array of tools from molecular and synthetic biology to -omics technologies. The chances of a product being based on a single GR are rare; being based on a single piece of DSI, effectively impossible. Yet to mandate benefit-sharing from these rare events would require tracking and tracing *all* DSI from open access infrastructures, because one does not know what will be used until the very end of the research and development process.

Life scientists use hundreds of millions of sequence, protein, small molecule, structural, and pathway data points to decide what hypotheses to pursue and which ones to abandon. They build consensus sequences based on thousands of DSI entries and then adapt them synthetically to optimize expression or folding.

For example, just as ChatGPT is disrupting numerous fields, artificial intelligence is revolutionizing biology. Deep Mind uses over 300 million sequences and hundreds of thousands of 3D crystal structures to predict virtual protein structures¹⁵ for drug discovery and beyond. The output of AI is based on multiple streams of biological data, none of which belongs to a single country or UN forum. As such, tracking and tracing sequence use is impractical. Taken together, these integrative analyses and outcomes are unlikely to produce benefit-sharing unless we build a radically different framework fit for the future.

Recommendation 4: Re-define the unit of benefit-sharing

A benefit-sharing approach based on individual sequences as the "unit" of benefit-sharing is incompatible with the nature of life sciences research. The COP15 decision recognized that for DSI, where the complexity of the dataset and user community is in the "big data" sphere (billions of data points), a transaction-based-benefit-sharing mechanism is simply not realistic. A new DSI benefit-sharing mechanism should reflect the value of the global bio-dataset. Furthermore, as users employ the global dataset, harmonization of benefit-sharing obligations across multiple fora will be essential to maximize user compliance and minimize transaction costs.

Seize the moment to reset and redesign benefit-sharing

We believe that a multilateral benefit-sharing mechanism for DSI, reflecting the recommendations above, will far better achieve the objectives of the CBD and other UN fora than current ABS systems including dramatically increasing resource mobilization. Countries should also be given the opportunity to voluntarily include GR in the scope of the new multilateral mechanism. This would contribute to the harmonization and simplification of ABS crucial to making it truly effective and impactful.

The recommendations above would represent major changes in established negotiating positions. Considered together, they would require relaxation of control on one hand and a major expansion of scope and significant financial commitment on the other. In our view, these large-scale compromises can fundamentally reset the ABS paradigm to a meaningful, comprehensive contribution for conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.

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Table 1: Policy recommendations for the multilateral DSI benefit-sharing mechanism to address the limitations of existing ABS systems

Latent ABS Design Flaws	Recommendations for DSI benefit-sharing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High transaction costs ● Low levels of legal certainty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Radical simplification ● De-couple benefit-sharing from both access and individual products ● Calculate contributions at an aggregate level ● Confirm publicly-funded DSI will be made open access (subject to privacy, IPLC interests)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inadequate benefits delivered to-date ● Benefit-sharing base too narrow ● Avoidance of ABS frameworks is easy because of narrow scope 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broaden benefit-sharing scope to “universal” ● Include new actors in biodiversity use scope (including negative externalities)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No guarantee of benefits causes mistrust ● Mistrust leads to under-engagement and further restrictions on access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Guarantee benefits for agreed groups of recipients (e.g., least-developed countries and IPLCs) ● Allocate funds to dedicated “streams” (e.g., capacity building, conservation, sustainable use)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transactional model not suited to integrative systems-based biological innovation across all sources of biodiversity, data, and jurisdictions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Re-define the “unit” of benefit-sharing from single GR or single DSI to “global biodata set” ● Harmonize global bio-dataset usage rules across UN fora (CBD, WHO, BBNJ, FAO)